

A Descriptive Study to Correlate NLR with Left Ventricular Systolic Function after ACSSrikanth S¹, Puneet Dewan²¹MD Medicine²DNB Medicine

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are responsible for 32% of all deaths worldwide and are the number one cause of deaths globally not only in high-income countries but also in low- and middle-income nations. Recently, neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio (NLR) has been found to be a strong predictor of adverse outcomes after Acute coronary syndromes (ACS). The possible mechanism is inflammation associated with atherosclerosis and its acute manifestation. This ratio can be accessed easily and is inexpensive. However, the prognostic value of NLR over and above the traditional cardiac biomarkers is unknown.

Aims and Objectives: The aim of study was to evaluate the prognostic role of NLR in patients with ACS. To correlate NLR with existing ACS cardiac biomarkers and evaluate incremental value of NLR for predicting adverse clinical outcomes after ACS over traditional markers. To correlate NLR with ST segment score in ST elevation MI (STEMI) and with left ventricular systolic function after ACS.

Methodology: A total of 100 consecutive ACS patients were included in the study after screening for inclusion and exclusion criteria. Informed consent was taken from the patient. Besides the demographic history, cardiac risk factors, clinical presentation and diagnosis were noted for all. NLR calculated as total neutrophil count divided by total lymphocyte count was computed for all included patients. An assessment of the inflammatory markers like LDH and cardiac function parameters like CPK, CK-MB was done. All patients underwent 2D echocardiography by an experienced cardiologists and left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) was assessed for all. ST segment score was noted for patients with STEMI.

Results: NLR was positively correlated (significant statistically) with total leucocyte count (TLC) ($r = 0.28$), AST ($r = 0.37$), LDH ($r = 0.46$), CK-MB ($r = 0.35$), CPK ($r = 0.46$) and ST segment score ($r=0.56$). The P values for these correlations were <0.05 . NLR co-related negatively LVEF ($r = -0.26$) ($p < 0.05$). NLR was positively correlated with mortality status with a rho level of 0.27 suggestive of a moderate positive association between the two parameters. As the outcome status changed from survival to mortality, the NLR ratio was seen to increase. The results were significant statistically ($P=0.0058$). There was no significant correlation of the NLR ratio with the gender or comorbidity related predictors.

Interpretation and Conclusions: This study concludes that the NLR is a good predictor for myocardial damage as well as impaired cardiac contractility. The NLR can help in early prognostication of ACS severity as well and help initiate treatment therapies to prevent adverse outcomes like mortality. Its role in predicting adverse clinical outcomes can be utilized in improving the management protocols in cardiology units. The findings of our study are in accordance with the published national and international literature in this domain. We have limited Indian studies on this domain and our study adds to the limited pool of literature concerning NLR role in ACS outcome and severity prediction. Larger randomized trials with multicentric study designs need to be conducted to further validate the findings in this study. Incorporation of NLR as an early bedside investigation in risk stratification of the patients also needs to be explored further

Keywords: Acute coronary syndromes, Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio, Cardio vascular diseases, ST elevation MI.

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Introduction

Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, presenting a critical challenge in cardiovascular medicine. ACS encompasses a spectrum of conditions, including unstable angina, non-ST-segment eleva-

tion myocardial infarction (NSTEMI), and ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), all of which result from the rupture or erosion of an atherosclerotic plaque leading to myocardial ischemia. The management of ACS requires timely

intervention to restore blood flow and minimize myocardial damage. Left ventricular systolic function, typically assessed by parameters such as ejection fraction (EF), is a crucial determinant of prognosis in patients with ACS. Impaired left ventricular systolic function post-ACS is associated with increased risk of heart failure, arrhythmias, and death. Therefore, identifying markers that can predict left ventricular systolic function early after ACS can help in risk stratification and guide therapeutic strategies.

The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) has emerged as a potential inflammatory marker in various cardiovascular diseases. NLR, calculated as the ratio of neutrophil count to lymphocyte count in peripheral blood, reflects the balance between innate and adaptive immune responses. Elevated NLR has been associated with adverse outcomes in a range of cardiovascular conditions, including ACS. Given the role of inflammation in the pathogenesis and progression of atherosclerosis and myocardial injury, NLR may serve as a valuable biomarker in assessing the inflammatory status and predicting outcomes in patients with ACS.

Aim and Objectives

To correlate NLR with left ventricular systolic function after ACS

Methodology

All patients admitted to Command hospital (Air force) Bengaluru with the diagnosis of ACS were included in the study after informed consent. Patients diagnosed as ACS visiting emergency department were included in the study. NLR,

calculated as total neutrophil counts divided by total lymphocyte counts, will be computed from the absolute values of neutrophils and lymphocytes from the same blood sample collected at admission. Since the study was a descriptive study, so a sample of convenience was taken based on historical trends of ACS patients' turnout in the cardiology department of the hospital. The data was compiled and analyzed using MS Excel (R) office 365, GraphPad prism 8.4.2 and SPSS version 25.

Results

The study was performed at the Department of medicine in the command hospital, Bangalore on 100 consecutive patients who presented with ACS. Total number of patients included in the study were 100. It was seen that most of the patients (45%) in the study had STEMI (ST elevation MI) followed by NSTEMI seen in 38%. Unstable angina was seen in 17% patients. The average age of the patients was 55.32 ± 13.71 years with a range of 16 years to 82 years. The median age was 58 years with an interquartile range of 45 to 66.25 years. Most of the patients were over the age of 60 years (42%) followed by 40-60 years age group (40%). There was a male preponderance in the study (79%). The average BMI was 23.46 ± 2.21 kg/m² with a median BMI of 23.30 kg/m². The average NLR ratio was 6.78 ± 6.84 with a median ratio of 3.61.

Total number of patients included in the study were 100. It was seen that most of the patients (45%) in the study had STEMI (ST elevation MI) followed by NSTEMI seen in 38%. Unstable angina was seen in 17% patients as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Overall Patient profile

Total number of patients	100	
ACS Profile	Number	Percentage
NSTEMI	38	38
STEMI	45	45
Unstable Angina	17	17
Grand Total	100	100

A correlation of the NLR with the continuous predictor variables was done. It was seen in Table 2 that –

1. NLR was positively correlated (significant statistically) with the TLC ($r=0.28$), neutrophils ($r=0.81$), AST ($r=0.37$), LDH ($r=0.46$), CK-

MB ($r=0.35$), CPK ($r=0.46$) and ST segment deviation ($r=0.56$). The P values for these correlations were <0.05 .

2. NLR was negatively correlated with LVEF ($r=-0.2$). The P values for these correlations were <0.05 .

Table 2: NLR correlation with the predictor variables (continuous)

Predictor	Pearson r	95% CI	R squared	P value	Significant	Correlation
Demographic parameters						
Inflammatory/cardiac markers						
LDH	0.46	0.29 to 0.60	0.21	<0.0001	Yes	r
CK-MB	0.35	0.16 to 0.51	0.12	0.0004	Yes	r
CPK	0.46	0.29 to 0.61	0.22	<0.0001	Yes	r

Cardiac parameters						
EF (57-75%)	-0.26	-0.44 to -0.068	0.068	0.0087	Yes	r
ST segment score parameters						
ST segment score	0.56	0.31 to 0.73	0.31	<0.0001	Yes	r

An NLR correlation with the categorical predictors was also done using the spearman rank coefficient (rho). It was seen that –

1. NLR was positively correlated with mortality status with a rho level of 0.27 suggestive of a moderate positive association between the two parameters.

As the outcome status changed from survival to mortality, the NLR ratio was seen to increase. The results were significant statistically (P=0.0058).

2. There was no significant correlation of the NLR ration with the gender or comorbidity related predictors.

Figure 1: NLR and ST segment score

Figure 1 scatter plot shows that there is a positive correlation between NLR and ST segment elevation, meaning that as the NLR increases, the ST segment elevation also tends to increase. The R^2 value of 0.3086 suggests that while there is a noticeable correlation, other factors may also significantly influence ST segment elevation, as around 69.14% of the variability is not explained by NLR alone. The slope of the line (0.1577) indicates that for each unit increase in NLR, the ST segment elevation increases by approximately 0.1577 mm, on average. This analysis suggests that higher NLR is associated with greater ST segment elevation, which could have clinical implications in assessing and predicting cardiac events.

Discussion

NLR is a very well-established parameter for systemic inflammation. [5-17] it is a very readily available biomarker of systemic inflammation which can predict survival, independent of tumor or disease stage in various cancers and associates with cancer-related cachexia. Kamelia et. al. [17] showed that the NLR ratio can be used in the TBDM spectrum for predicting the systemic inflammation and is associated with recurrence and survival. The role of NLR in various cardiac conditions has been explored extensively by studies

in recent times. Chen Chen et al [15] in their study showed that the NLR is a strong predictor of myocardial damage in acute myocardial patients. High NLR are associated with myocardial dysfunction in all the patients. Severe inflammation (NLR) can predict the consequence of the heart in patients with coronary syndrome. Arbel et al [7] showed that Higher Neutrophil/Lymphocyte Ratio Is Related to Lower Ejection Fraction and Higher Long-term All-Cause Mortality in ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction Patients.

Because of limited literature on NLR utility in Indian subset of cardiac patients, we performed at the Department of medicine in the command hospital, Bangalore on 100 consecutive patients who presented with signs and symptoms suggestive of acute coronary syndrome (ACS).

A holistic spectrum of ACS patients was used which comprised of the mostly STEMI patients (45%) and NSTEMI patients (38%). We included 17% patients in the study who had unstable angina. Overall Indian studies have also reported a predominance of the STEMI in patients presenting with ACS. Patel and Mohanan et al [18] showed that 37% of the patients were STEMI in their study followed by 31% NSTEMI patients. Chen Chen et al [15] showed that the mean age of ACS patients

included in their study for the NLR evaluation, was 61.38 (± 9.84) years, and 417 (58.32%) of these patients were men. This corroborated with our study where male preponderance was seen. Mohanan et al [18] in a similar study based out of Kerala similarly showed that the mean age of participants was 60.4 (12.1) years, and more than three-quarters of these patients were men. Chen Chen et al [15] showed that The NLR ranges from 0.50 to 46 (medium \pm SD, 2.76 ± 2.96) in 715 patients. NLR positively correlated with myocardial damage (NLR vs. CK-MB: $p < 0.0001$) but negatively correlated with myocardial function (NLR vs. EF: $p < 0.0001$; NLR vs. FS: $p < 0.0001$). Myocardial damage markers (CK, CK-MB, ASL, LDH) were significantly increased, and cardiac contractile parameters (EF and FS) were reduced at $NLR > 2.76$ compared to those of $NLR < 2.76$.

Our study also showed that NLR could also be a good predictor of the ST segment score as suggested by the fact that the NLR was positively correlated with the ST Segment score ($r=0.56$). It can, therefore, be a good marker for the STEMI patients where severity of myocardial damage in STEMI can be prognosticated using this simple cost-effective test. NLR was positively correlated with mortality status with a rho level of 0.27 suggestive of a moderate positive association between the two parameters. As the outcome status changed from survival to mortality, the NLR ratio was seen to increase. The results were significant statistically ($P=0.0058$). This suggests that the NLR ratio is a good marker for the mortality prediction in the ACS patients. Arbel et al [7] showed that Patients undergoing STEMI were put into two groups (high/low NLR), and logistic regression was used to assess in-hospital complications and LVEF based on NLR. The results showed that higher NLR values (>6.5) were associated with lower EF and increased 30 days and 5-year mortality. This corresponding cut off was 3.47 for our study.

Comparative profile – NLR higher levels with lower levels: Using the cut off of NLR as 4 as per Chen Chen [15], we divided the patients into two groups. We observed that the AST levels were significantly higher for the patients with NLR more than 4 (89.22 vs 48.89, $P=0.0003$). The cardiac markers for myocardial damage like CPK (322.07 vs 141.81, $P<0.0001$) and CK-MB (90.46 vs 54.02, $P<0.0001$) and the inflammatory markers like LDH (353.78 vs 257.52, $P=0.0002$) were significantly higher for the patients with NLR more than 4. The cardiac function parameters or cardiac contractility indicators like EF was significantly worse for patients with NLR more than 4. The results were significant statistically ($P<0.05$). The average ST segment score for the patients with NLR more than 4 was significantly higher compared to the other groups (4.48 vs 3.25, $P<0.0001$). The above findings are suggestive of the fact that as the NLR

levels increase, the cardiac function tends to worsen, and cardiac myocardial inflammatory damage increases. This trend is valid for the STEMI as well where the extent of severity, as suggested by the ST segment elevation, increased as the NLR levels increased. We observed that the mortality in the study was 06%.

The average NLR levels were higher for the patients experiencing mortality suggesting a possible role of NLR in prediction of mortality and poor prognosis. Ahmed A Reda et. al. in their Egypt based study on ACS showed that Preprocedural N/L ratio was an independent prognostic factor for both in-hospital mortality and adverse outcomes among the STEMI patients who underwent primary PCI during the hospital stay. N/L ratio was an independent predictor of no-reflow/reflow and angiographic grade after PCI. [19] Sheng et al investigated the association of NLR with long-term mortality after STEMI treated with primary PCI. The study tested the hypothesis that in the acute phase of STEMI, whether NLR could be used to predict long-term prognosis. Their results indicate that patients in the highest NLR quartile were 4 times more likely to die during hospitalization and during long-term follow-up.20

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, we could conclude that the NLR is a good predictor for myocardial damage as well as impaired cardiac contractility. The NLR can help in early prognostication of STEMI severity. It's role in predicting adverse clinical outcomes can be utilized in improving the management protocols in cardiology units. The findings of our study are in accordance with the published national and international literature in this domain. We have limited Indian studies on this domain and our study adds to the limited pool of literature concerning NLR role in ACS outcome and severity prediction. Larger randomized trials with multicentric study designs need to be conducted to further validate the findings in this study. Incorporation of NLR as an early inexpensive and readily available prognostic marker in ACS can help stratify the ACS patients in resource deprived countries like India and hence needs further exploration.

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